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OIKONET A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

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Deliverable Administration and Summary

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Editor	Henrich Pifko				
Work Programme Description	Exhibitions of the processes and results of housing related projects at specific locations, in Europe and outside. The exhibitions will have a unified format which will include contents produced by the different sub-networks applicable to the project and will be adapted to the local language. The exhibition contents will be also available in digital format in the network portal.				
Comments	An earlier version of this document was delivered with the interim report in April 2015.				

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5	2017-02-26	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)	Final editing
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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document summarizes the work done in the OIKONET project to disseminate the project outcomes in exhibitions taking place at the partner organizations and elsewhere. A total of 20 exhibitions organized by 10 OIKONET partners were displayed during the project lifetime. The contents of the exhibitions encompass student works carried out in the joint pedagogical activities (learning spaces, workshops) and research work conducted at the partner organizations. Most of the posters produced for these exhibitions were dedicated to displaying the work carried out during the pedagogical activities. Some of the exhibitions have been replicated at different locations. In particular, the work produced in the Lisbon Workshop –in the preparatory activities and during in workshop itself- has been displayed at various institutions, as well as external partner organizations.

The posters presented at the different exhibitions are available on the Sharepoint file sharing system for partners to use them in later exhibitions. They can also be facilitated to third parties upon request. A selection of these posters is collated in the Appendix.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

The work carried out in OIKONET was displayed in a series of exhibitions during the three years of the project lifetime. They were organized in conjunction with OIKONET events (conferences, workshops, meetings), in partner organizations, as well as in other external events and places. The exhibitions helped to summarize the work done, to present it to partners and to third parties. The target groups are faculty members and students in the partner organizations, professionals (architects, planners involved in the case studies addressed in the project), and citizens (participants in community actions related to the project).

2.2 Contribution of partners

In total, there 20 exhibitions were organized by the 10 OIKONET partners:

- P1 LA SALLE- School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain (5 exhibitions)
 - Exhibition of OIKONET work during the first international conference in Barcelona, School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 24-27 September 2014
 - A exhibition done by students and teachers in the learning space “Thinking Dwelling”, School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 19-30 October 2015
 - Exhibition of the work done by students in the learning space “Urban Systems”, School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, La Salle, 8-15 February 2016
 - Exhibition of the work done by students in the learning space “Thinking Dwelling”, School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 14-30 September 2016
 - Exhibition of the work done by students in the learning space “Urban Systems”, Civic Centre Can Felipa, Barcelona, January 2017
- P2 ETSA-UPV- School of Architecture of Valencia, Spain (3 exhibitions)
 - Exhibition of the work done in the learning space “Introduction to housing”. School of Architecture, Valencia, 19 February- 31 March 2015
 - Exhibition of the work done produced in the Lisbon Workshop, School of Architecture, Valencia, March 23 – April 20 2015
 - Exhibition of the posters presented at the first international conference in Barcelona, School of Architecture, Valencia, March 27 – April 20 2015
- P3 FASTU- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, Bratislava, Slovakia (2 exhibitions)
 - Exhibition of works produced in the learning space “Habitat Regeneration Strategies”, the Bratislava Petržalka central development axis. Bratislava, ARCHA municipal exhibition room, February 27 – March 3 2015
 - Exhibition of the work done by OIKONET partners at the second international conference, Bratislava, September 2015
- P4 KUL- Faculty of Architecture, KU Leuven, Gent/Brussels, Belgium (1 exhibition)
 - Exhibition of the work produced by the students of KU Leuven in the learning space “Small is Power”, Antwerp, 11 December 2015 to 17 March 2016

- P9 UTH- Department of Architecture - University of Thessaly, Volos, Greece (1 exhibition)
 - An exhibition of the work carried out in the OIKONET project in the Department of Architecture, University of Thessaly, Volos, 23 -30 May 2016
- P16 UCLAN- Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, University of Central Lancashire (1 exhibition)
 - Exhibition of the work done by OIKONET partners at the third international conference, Manchester, September 2016
- P18 UGA- Institut d'Urbanisme de Grenoble, Université Grenoble Alpes, France (1 exhibition)
 - Exhibition of work learning space “Habitat Regeneration Strategies”, at UGA in Grenoble, 18-19 December 2014
- P25 ISCTE-IUL University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal (4 exhibitions)
 - Exhibition of the works produced in the context of the first international workshop in Lisbon, 19 July-22 September 2014
 - Exhibition of the results of the Lisbon workshop in Greenfest, Estoril, 10-12 October, 2014
 - Exhibition of prototypes produced in the Lisbon workshop at the conference “For a more inclusive society”, ISCTE-IUL, December 1-5, 2014
 - Stand at Erasmus Mobility using the prototypes fabricated at the Lisbon, ISCTE-IUL, February 15, 2015
- P26 AF BELGRADE- Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, Serbia (1 exhibition)
 - Exhibition of the preparatory work done for the third international workshop in Belgrade, Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, 6-11 June 2016
- P29 DIT- School of Architecture, Dublin Institute of Technology, Ireland (1 exhibition)
 - Exhibition of the results of the Lisbon workshop in Linen Hall, DIT, Dublin. November 2014

Furthermore, most partners have contributed to these exhibitions preparing posters about their research and pedagogical activities.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The exhibitions mostly displayed the work carried out in the subnetworks Housing Research and Pedagogical Activities. They helped partners to learn about the work done in other institutions, and to disseminate the project results in the partner organizations and to third parties.

3 EXHIBITIONS

The exhibitions carried out during the project are summarized next.

3.1 First international workshop, Lisbon

Exhibition of the work carried out during the [first international workshop in Lisbon](#) presented at the end of the workshop. The exhibition included posters of the work done by students in the preparatory activities. ISCTE-IUL, Lisbon, 19 July-22 September 2014.

Figure 1. Lisbon Workshop exhibition at ISCTE-IUL, Lisbon

3.2 First international conference, Barcelona

Poster exhibition during the first international conference in Barcelona. It was divided into two blocks: Lisbon Workshop and summary of the work carried out at each organization related to the OIKONET project. School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 24-27 September 2014.

Figure 2. Exhibition during the first international conference, School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona

3.3 Greenfest, Estoril

The full scale prototypes developed in the OIKONET Lisbon workshop were chosen to represent the pedagogical innovation, sustainability and social responsibility of the ISCTE-IUL at the Greenfest festival in Estoril, Portugal. The display received the award for the best stand. Estoril, 10-12 October 2014.

<http://www.greenfest.pt/>

Figure 3. ISCTE-IUL Stand at GREENFEST'2014 – Green Stand Award

3.4 Contemporary Living Patterns, Dublin

An exhibition of posters on the work completed in the Lisbon Workshop was on display in the ground floor gallery of Linen Hall in DIT Bolton Street in Dublin, November 2014.

<http://dit.ie/update/19-11-14/posterexhibitiononcontemporarylivingpatternsinmasshousingineurope/>

Figure 4. Dublin exhibition

3.5 “For a more inclusive society” Conference, Lisbon

The prototypes produced in the Lisbon Workshop prototypes were chosen to represent the ISCTE-IUL at the conference “For a more inclusive society”, ISCTE-IUL, December 1-5, 2014.

3.6 Urban Morphology and Regeneration of Riverbanks

Exhibition of posters of the work completed by students from UGA in relation to the on-line learning space “Habitat Regeneration Strategies”, UGA, Grenoble, 18-19 December 2014.

Figure 5. Grenoble exhibition

3.7 Erasmus Mobility ISCTE-IUL Stand, Lisbon

ISCTE-IUL stand at the Erasmus Mobility Fair incorporated the prototypes produced in the Lisbon Workshop prototypes to attract the attention of potential Erasmus students, Lisbon, February 15, 2015.

Figure 6. ISCTE-IUL stand at Erasmus Mobility fair

3.8 Introduction to Housing, Valencia

Poster exhibition of the the work done in the learning space “Introduction to housing”. School of Architecture, Valencia, 19 February – 31 March 2015.

Figure 7. Exhibition at the School of Architecture of Valencia.

3.9 Habitat Regeneration Strategies, Bratislava

Exhibition documenting the work carried out by FASTU in the collaborative learning space “Habitat Regeneration Strategies” dedicated to the study of Petržalka central development axis. ARCHA municipal exhibition room, Bratislava, February 27 – March 3 2015.

http://www.fa.stuba.sk/sk/dianie-na-fakulte/aktuality/learning-space-habitat-regeneration-strategies.html?page_id=3794

Figure 8. Opening of the Bratislava exhibition

3.10 Contemporary living patterns, Valencia

Exhibition of the work done produced in the Lisbon Workshop, School of Architecture, Valencia, March 23 – April 20 2015.

Figure 9. Exhibition of the Lisbon Workshop in the School of Architecture of Valencia

3.11 Global Dwelling, Valencia

An exhibition of the posters displayed at the first international conference in Barcelona, School of Architecture of Valencia, March 27 – April 20 2015.

Figure 10. Posters presented in the Barcelona conference at the School of Architecture of Valencia

3.12 Second international conference, Bratislava

An exhibition of posters reflecting the work done by the OIKONET partners in pedagogy and research was on display during the second OIKONET conference on “Global Dwelling”, Bratislava, in September 2015.

Figure 11. Opening of the exhibition at the Bratislava conference

3.13 Thinking Dwelling (first edition), Barcelona

A poster exhibition of the work done by students and teachers in the first edition of the “Thinking Dwelling” learning space, School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 19-30 October 2015.

Figure 12. Poster exhibition “Thinking Dwelling”, School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona

3.14 Small is Power, Antwerp

An exhibition of the work produced by the students of KU Leuven in the learning space “Small is Power”, Antwerp, 11 December 2015 - 17 March 2016.

Figure 13. Exhibition “Small is Power”, Antwerp

As one of the learning activities in the OIKONET “SMALL is POWER” learning space, MSc. students from KU Leuven were asked to design and produce an installation in an historical shop front in Antwerp. The installation challenged the notion of the house as a passive element in the development of public space. The purpose was to explore the constituting elements of the relation between the house and the public realm, between inside and outside, reflecting the transition from private space to collective space and the role architecture plays in fostering a dialogue between both.

<https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=10208292913388478&set=gm.635033949970842&type=3>

3.15 Urban Systems (first edition), Barcelona

The work done by students in the first edition of the learning space “Urban Systems” was presented at an exhibition in the School of Architecture La Salle, 8-15 February 2016.

Figure 14. Poster exhibition “Urban Systems”, Barcelona

3.16 OIKONET project exhibition, Volos

An exhibition of the work carried out in the OIKONET project has taken place at the Department of Architecture, University of Thessaly, Volos, from 23 -30 May 2016.

<http://www.arch.uth.gr/en/activities/1245>

Figure 15. Announcement in the website of the Department of Architecture, University of Thessaly

Figure 16. Exhibition space, Department of Architecture, University of Thessaly, Volos

3.17 Thinking Dwelling (second edition), Barcelona

An exhibition with the contributions of participants in the second edition of the “Thinking Dwelling” program has been on display at the School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 14-30 September 2016.

Figure 17. Second edition of the “Thinking Dwelling” program, School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona

3.18 Poster exhibition at the 3rd international workshop, Belgrade

Exhibition of the preparatory works produced for the third international workshop, Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, 6-11 June 2016.

Figure 18. Exhibition in during the Belgrade workshop

3.19 Third international conference, Manchester

During the third international conference in Manchester, there was an exhibition of the work of project partners, Manchester, September 23, 2016.

Figure 19. Exhibition during the third international workshop in Manchester

3.20 Urban Systems (second edition), Barcelona

The work done in the second edition of the learning space “Urban Systems” was presented by students in the civic centre Can Felipa, Barcelona, in January 2017 – their works were exhibited until April 2017.

Figure 20. Presentations and discussion of the second edition of the learning space “Urban Systems”, Can Felipa, Barcelona

Figure 21. Poster exhibition in Can Felipa, Barcelona

The students presented their analyses of four axes integrated in the urban structure of Barcelona (Rambla Guipúscoa, Rambla del Poble Nou, Rambla del Raval and Avinguda Mistral) and their transformation proposals to contribute to making the city more liveable. Representatives of neighbours' associations and urban activists attended the presentations and participated in a debate with students and teachers. The work presented in this event was then discussed in a colloquium broadcasted by Radio Ciutat Vella, a local radio station. An exhibition of the students' works was on display during April 2017.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The use of a unified template for all the posters presented in the exhibitions (vertical A0, with the project logo and related project information) has contributed to creating a project identity. For students, synthesizing the work done in the pedagogical activities in one poster has been an exercise in visual communication and graphic design. Seeing posters produced by different partners together has enabled students and teachers alike to appreciate which posters transmitted the ideas more effectively. Even though it is often taken for granted, producing a well-designed poster is not an easy task, neither for students nor for teachers.

The replication of exhibitions at different institutions has been an effective strategy to disseminate the work within the consortium, which could be done with relatively little resources. These exhibitions have helped to disseminate OIKONET within each organization, by letting other students and teachers who are not directly involved in the project activities know about the work done in the project.

APPENDIX A. SELECTION OF POSTERS

A.1 Posters at the Barcelona Conference

Selected posters from the Barcelona conference poster exhibition.

A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

[Zvětšit na úroveň stránky (Ctrl+0)]

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

SELF-SUFFICIENT LIVING CELL

Learning-by-doing students' project

Sašo Medved, Suzana Kranjc
www.medi@fdm.uni-lj.si, suzana.kranjc@fdm.uni-lj.si

How it started ?
Project began in October 2010. Students of the Faculty of Architecture form a team and within the lectures building physics and building services lead by professor Sašo Medved participating in the project. Cell architectural design was made within the seminar led by architect assistant Igor Štepec.

How it works ?
The Cell is heated by three different solar water and air heating systems, while for the power supply photovoltaic system is used. A system for collecting rain water is installed, waste water is treated in a constructed wetland. That's why the Cell is not connected to any municipal district system. All five units have been designed in collaboration with more than twenty industrial partners, on the pluggin in the Societal Cashmere near Ljubljana. At the end of May 2012 all units were transported to a location at the park at Trnovo near Poljansko Street in Ljubljana and available for the visitors since then.

Where can you find more data ?
Information about planning principles, building process and installed technologies are available on site www.stu.uni-lj.si/med

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
Show of Architects in Ljubljana, Slovenia, 29th-30th September 2014

For more information please visit the website: www.oikonet.org or contact: info@oikonet.org

A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava

URBAN RENEWAL AND SUSTAINABLE HOUSING

Urban Renewal of Part of an Hospital to Housing Community in Uherské Hradiště Czech Republic

Juraj Furdík, Zuzana Kevčová
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How it started ?
The ultimate goal was self sufficiency and mobility of the Cell. Therefore it consists of five modules, each with its own unique role: residential unit, bedroom in the attic, sanitary unit with shower and toilet, technology unit with kitchen, solar heating and photovoltaic systems and rainwater collection and supply system and the attic as the technological unit with a hot air solar heating system. All units are made by timber frames. Several insulation materials were used such as mineral wool, cellulose and vacuum panels. Students were involved in all building phases, including workshops organized by industrial partners.

What's going on now?
Since the opening in May 2012, project was presented in several articles and TV shows and at international and domestic conferences. Even more important is that Cell attracts very different visitors: from general public to experts, from primary school pupils to professional lecturers and university students, from Slovenia and abroad.

Where can you find more data ?
Information about planning principles, building process and installed technologies are available on site www.stu.uni-lj.si/med

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
Show of Architects in Ljubljana, Slovenia, 29th-30th September 2014

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OIKONET
A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

University of Cyprus

DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS (UCY), NICOSIA

RE-DESIGNING THE VOIDS
A new way of living

MARIA CHRISTOFI
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The following study investigates the characteristics of an empty space in the context of Nicosia in Cyprus, a complex in contrast with the city's dense and built character. The study is examined as an element involved in the design of clear stages and experience.

The outcome of this research and study does not aim to a solution but to a possible future scenario when dealing with such cases in order to investigate issues of living and flexibility in the urban landscape through the study of their intrinsic programs. Thus, through an analysis and solutions proposed and tested by the participant, urban projects are developed in the city center strategies reported from the main features of the specific site study through the proposed questions about the concept of porous and liquid urban forms (P&L U&F, Liquid Voids).

high built, highlighting urban health, urban transformation, urban design, planning

river path, collecting river gate, connecting overflow paths, leaving

MEGACONCEPT ANALYSIS

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 23rd-26th September 2014

For more information please visit the website www.oikonet.org or contact: info@oikonet.org

LifeLong Learning Programme

OIKONET
A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

ARQ

School of Architecture, Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico, San Juan

CIVIC HOUSING
Guidelines from community participation for the design of collective housing

Prof. Omara Rivera Crego
omara@arq.uspr.edu

COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION
FOCUS: 1998

Community participation in the design process is a key element in the development of collective housing. This research explores the role of community participation in the design of collective housing, focusing on the experience of the Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico.

GLADIOLAS PRODUCCION
with landscape program

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 23rd-26th September 2014

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LifeLong Learning Programme

OIKONET
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POUS

POLIS University, International School of Architecture and Urban Development Policies, Tirana

URBAN AND HOUSING PHENOMENA IN THE CITY OF TIRANA

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GROWTH & EXPANSION OF TIRANA CITY

SDx and the City
How values shape the urban development
Spiral Dynamics

STORY OF AN APARTMENT

VISIONING FUTURE CITIES

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 23rd-26th September 2014

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LifeLong Learning Programme

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TU

Institute of Architecture, Technical University Berlin

DEFINING POROSITY IN HOUSING
Porosity Design Tool in Low-cost Multiunit Housing of Dense Areas

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Introduction and Research Background

Dense Urban Areas

Diversity of Habitation

Housing Typologies

Correlation: Housing-Porosity Examples

Literature cited

Conclusions

Porosity - Term, Definition, Characteristics and Historical Review

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 23rd-26th September 2014

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LifeLong Learning Programme

Lisbon Workshop July 14th-19th 2014

Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ISCTE- University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

This international workshop on **sustainable and collaborative housing design** is organized by the project "OIKONET: a global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning", co-financed by the European Union. The objective of the workshop will be to develop a cross-disciplinary dialogue aimed at finding answers to the meanings, ways and forms of contemporary living patterns of mass housing in Europe.

Two neighborhoods in Lisbon will be used as case studies: one which is representative of the formal mass housing - "Portela de Sacavém" - and another one - "Bairro da Liberdade" - which is a typical neighbourhood of informal mass housing.

The overall housing design process will be addressed, starting **from participation and ending with digital fabrication**. Design strategies will be based on: Co-creation methods (community participation, participatory design theory and techniques, generative design research), Contemporary living patterns (social housing, housing and quality of life, domestic scenarios, new ways of life, new family structures, the changing of demographic trends and new housing needs; energy efficiency and construction materials), and Digital tools CAD / CAM (parametric design, modular systems and digital fabrication).

The ultimate goal is to develop an **evolving housing design using prefabricated wood panels**, to re-adapt pre-existing dwellings to contemporary living patterns and to produce new incrementally built homes as a response to today's living conditions.

For more information please visit the website www.oikonet.org or contact: Info@oikonet.org

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OIKONET
A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

ETSAP UPV, UCY, AF Belgrade

INTRODUCTION TO HOUSING
A collaborative learning space on the fundamentals of housing design and representation

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FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
School of Architecture La Salla, Barcelona, 25th-26th September 2014

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A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

College of Architecture and Urban Planning CAUP, Tongji University, Shanghai

YOUTH HOUSING TRANSITIONS
Young people in Serbia: Co-housing model implementation alternatives

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Key words: youth transitions, housing pathways, Serbian youth, future directions, co-housing, peer-shared households

Introduction: This research project is a part of a larger project titled "Youth Transitions in Urban Housing" which aims to explore the housing needs and preferences of young people in urban areas. The project is funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Problem: The research addresses the challenges young people face in finding affordable and suitable housing, particularly in urban areas where housing costs are high and space is limited. It explores how co-housing models can provide a viable alternative to traditional housing arrangements.

Methodology: The research uses a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, including interviews, focus groups, and surveys. Data was collected from 312 participants across different age groups and housing situations.

Results: The research identifies key factors influencing housing transitions, such as income, education, and social networks. It also highlights the benefits of co-housing, including shared resources, community support, and reduced costs.

Conclusions: The findings suggest that co-housing models can be a successful way to address the housing needs of young people in urban areas. However, successful implementation requires careful planning and support from local authorities and the private sector.

Future research: Further research is needed to explore the long-term impacts of co-housing and to identify ways to scale up these models in other urban contexts.

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
School of Architecture La Salla, Barcelona, 25th-26th September 2014

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OIKONET
A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Aarhus School of Architecture, Denmark

SPATIAL PLASTICITY
studies in the configuration of the space for living

Ph.D.-student Sina Henkel Schultz
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FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
School of Architecture La Salla, Barcelona, 25th-26th September 2014

For more information please visit the website www.oikonet.org or contact: Info@oikonet.org

A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

SELF-SUFFICIENT LIVING CELL
Learning-by-doing students' project

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How it started ?

Project began in October 2010. Students of the Faculty of Architecture form a team and within the lecture Building physics and Building services, lead by professor Saso Medved participating in the project. Cell architectural design was made within the seminar led by architect assistant Igor Štalič.

Energy efficiency measures and technology systems design were done by students of architecture and mechanical engineering during curriculum. Renewable energy sources in the meantime, 830,000,000 students from 8 countries planned versus "Self-sufficient living cell" during design IACS Edu education materials were used and tested.

How it was built ?

The ultimate goal was self-sufficiency and mobility of the Cell. Therefore it consists of five modules, each with its own unique role: residential unit, bedroom in the attic, sanitary unit with shower and toilet, technology unit with kitchen, solar heating and photovoltaic systems and rainwater collection and supply system and the attic of the technological unit with a hot air solar heating system. All units are made by timber frames. Several insulation materials were used such as mineral wool, cellulose and vacuum panels. Students were involved in all building phases, including workshops organized by industrial partners.

How it works ?

The Cell is heated by three different solar water and air heating systems, while for the power supply photovoltaic system is used. A system for collecting rain water is installed, waste water is treated in a constructed wetland. That's why the Cell is not connected to any municipal district system. All the units have been designed in collaboration with more than twenty industrial partners, on the plot in the Srednje Gameljne near Ljubljana. At the end of May 2012 all units were transported to a location in the park at Trnovo near Žiljopogovje Street in Ljubljana and available for the visitors since then.

What's going on now?

Since the opening in May 2012, project was presented in several articles and TV shows and at international and domestic conferences. Even more important is that Cell attracts very different visitors: from general public to experts, from primary school pupils to professional scholars and university students, from Slovenia and abroad.

Where can you find more data ?

Information about planning principles, building process and related technologies are available on site www.ee.isi.uni-lj.si/cell

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 25th-26th September 2014

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A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering

ROLES IN THE NETWORK
UCLan - GBACE is leading WP2: HOUSING RESEARCH, and contributes to WP7: Dissemination and WP8: Exploitation.

PARTICIPANTS
Professor Karim Hadjiri, leader of WP2. Isaiiah Oluremi Durosaiye, PhD candidate & research assistant

OUTPUT

- Literature review
- Readings
- WikiMedia entries
- Research matrix
- Subnetwork meetings

WP2 Deliverables

Deliverable	Lead	Start	End	Status
D1: Literature Review	K. Hadjiri	2012	2013	Completed
D2: Readings	K. Hadjiri	2012	2013	Completed
D3: Research Matrix	K. Hadjiri	2012	2013	Completed

Partners' Research Matrix

Partner	WP2	WP7	WP8
1. GBACE, UCLan (Lead)	Yes	Yes	Yes
2. School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain	Yes	Yes	Yes
3. Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden	Yes	Yes	Yes
4. Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies (IHUS), Erasmus University, Rotterdam, The Netherlands	Yes	Yes	Yes
5. University of Ljubljana (UJ), Slovenia	Yes	Yes	Yes
6. Riga Technical University, Latvia	Yes	Yes	Yes
7. Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia	Yes	Yes	Yes
8. Centre for Urban and Regional Research (CURR), Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE), Budapest, Hungary	Yes	Yes	Yes

WP2 PARTNERS

- GBACE, UCLan (Lead)
- School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain
- Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden
- Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies (IHUS), Erasmus University, Rotterdam, The Netherlands
- University of Ljubljana (UJ), Slovenia
- Riga Technical University, Latvia
- Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia
- Centre for Urban and Regional Research (CURR), Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE), Budapest, Hungary

Associate Partners

- Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Russia
- Faculty of Architecture & Urbanism, University of Chile, Chile
- Faculty of Architecture, Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico, Rico
- UIN-Habitat, Nairobi, Kenya
- Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus, Cyprus

Oikonet Digital Platform

Oikonet entry

Oikonet Website: oikonet.org

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Faculty of Architecture, Bialystok University of Technology

THRESHOLD MATTERS
Explore the realities of the private to the public

Aleksander Acemovic, Katarzyna Acemovic, Adam Jakubowski
acemovic@buet.pl, katarzyna.acemovic@gmail.com, adam.jakubowski@gmail.com

Participation in the „Threshold Matters“ learning space development.

Design studio project: „BLURRED FUNCTION SPACE“ conducted with a group of students at BUT.

The goal: Developing the concepts of interrelation between private and public space in the given urban concepts

Collaboration scheme

Schedule of the spring semester

Week	Activity	Responsible
1	Introduction	Aleksander Acemovic
2	Concepting/initialisation	Katarzyna Acemovic
3	Concept development	Adam Jakubowski
4	Concept finalisation	Aleksander Acemovic
5	Concept presentation	Aleksander Acemovic
6	Concept presentation	Aleksander Acemovic
7	Concept presentation	Aleksander Acemovic
8	Concept presentation	Aleksander Acemovic
9	Concept presentation	Aleksander Acemovic
10	Concept presentation	Aleksander Acemovic
11	Concept presentation	Aleksander Acemovic
12	Concept presentation	Aleksander Acemovic

OIKONET Course projects

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A.2 Contemporary Living Patterns

Posters presenting the work done in the Lisbon Workshop.

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"Bairns de Liberdade: creating patterns of improvement"
Marina Casale, Caroline Mollers, Georgia Papanicolaou, Orhan Karak, Aleksandar Cvek, Mark Spilo

Throughout the session, Bairns de Liberdade successfully improved beyond its original core with the combination of digital rights, flexibility to generate better conditions in the neighbourhood and the design adaptation of publicly owned land for the reconstruction of existing neighbourhoods, by the removal of barriers. It's important that it is a solution for the housing need to create a common space.

WORKSHOP: Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ICTE - University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal, July 14th-15th 2014

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"PORTELA: Adaptable Living"
Ana Sofia Simões, Cláudia Camaral, Frederik Peter Karsgaard, Eze Arkovici, Hala Sarrif, Yusef El-B

WORKSHOP: Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ICTE - University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal, July 14th-15th 2014

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LIBERDADE - THE ROOFBOX
João Luis Lemos Lobo - Daniel Augusto G. Araújo - Vasco Reis - Hugo Martins - Emily Dickinson - Lúcia Gomes

ANALYSIS

PLANS

DESIGN

SECTION

DETAILS

WORKSHOP: Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ICTE - University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal, July 14th-15th 2014

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Portela: S.I. Box - a package for social interaction
Andrzej Kalk, Dede Guclu, Ihaba Dinkiewicz, Jan Bylica-Kowalski, Leona Hajos, Mircea Cankovic

COMMON SPACE, FLEXIBILITY, TRANSFORMATION, SLEND MODULES, URBAN GARDENING.
A proposal about an interior common space that will improve the inhabitants social life. Common kitchens and multifunctional areas reflect a co-housing concept. The space transforms itself according to the residents' needs.

EXISTING SITES

PROPOSAL

MODULE VARIANTS

WORKSHOP: Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ICTE - University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal, July 14th-15th 2014

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"BAIRRO DA LIBERDADE: The Garden of Eden"
Pavel Dobřinský, Andrej Konec, Sereia Afari, Diana Galvão, Alina Dimitrova-Bogdanova, Andrew O'Shea, Ana Lopes

The project in Bairro da Liberdade fits in really bad conditions. There are too many people with low to low income, especially pensioners. We decided to give them a right to live in a better place. In the future, they will have more public space for their activities, which is not in place. A common area will be created by the existing houses and will be used for the people to live in. The idea is to create a new living environment and to create a new living environment. The idea is to create a new living environment and to create a new living environment. The idea is to create a new living environment and to create a new living environment.

Site plan
Site problems, level of imperfection, solutions

Floor plans
Sections

Design of the window system as an exterior red area / garden area

WORKSHOP: Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ICTP University Institute of Urban Policy, July 19-19-2014

For more information please visit the website: www.oikonet.org or contact: info@oikonet.org

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PORTELA: A contemporary solution for a modern design.
Carlo Scarpa, Sava, Luka Koli, Bruno Taut, Alvaro Siza, EM Starnik, Milica Jankovic

The ever aging population of Portela calls for a different type of house: one to accommodate the elderly people living alone; one for exchange activities; one for the new families of 2 or 4 people that were attracted there due to the purchase price; and finally another for the one who wants to live in the city of the future but, together with the old and new in the same building, form a family group. We propose a solution composed of many different houses, all of them give you the opportunity to make the most of your own through the use of a modular construction system. This system is arranged in a grid, so we can create more sections and still provide a lot of freedom to the user. The floor plans started as open spaces and as the typologies were developed, private areas rose from the empty spaces.

WORKSHOP: Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ICTP University Institute of Urban Policy, July 19-19-2014

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HOUSE 1, Bairro da Liberdade, Lisboa, Portugal
GROUP 1: GONCALVES, TROLSBYCH, CORDEIRO, LIMA, CRISTINA AGUIAR, MALCZONKA, BULGARIANA, TUGA CAVALHEIRO

WORKSHOP: Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ICTP University Institute of Urban Policy, July 19-19-2014

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"One Floor, One Family" - Group D - Bairro da Portela de Sacavém
Natal Oliveira, Igor Kravtchuk, Nani Aw, Francisco Alves, Cláudio Pinheiro, Stefan Graunke, Hector Ruiz

WORKSHOP: Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe
ICTP University Institute of Urban Policy, July 19-19-2014

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A.3 Habitat Regeneration Strategies: Case study Bratislava Petržalka

Posters of the work done in the “Case study Bratislava Petržalka central development axis”:

A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava

APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN URBAN REGENERATION

Viera Jeklová, Iveta Ančiar
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SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
FA2011 - Faculty of Architecture Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, 24 - 25 September 2011

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Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava

SOLAR TOWN PLANNING

Sustainable urban intensification of existing housing estate Ostredky in Bratislava

Ján Legány, Peter Mergensstein
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Istanbul Technical University, Faculty of Architecture

URBAN CATALYST

Urban Catalyst and Beyond for Sustainable Urban Transformation in Istanbul

Assoc. Prof. Yasemin Altınser Bregger, Ph.D.
#yasemin@itu.edu.tr

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FA2011 - Faculty of Architecture Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, 24 - 25 September 2011

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Dublin School of Architecture, DIT, Ireland

HOUSING REGENERATION STRATEGIES

DIT student projects for Waterford City, Ireland

Jim Roche - Orta D' Donnell, Jim Ward
jim.roche@dit.ie

SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
FA2011 - Faculty of Architecture Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, 24 - 25 September 2011

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Faculty of Architecture Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, Slovakia
Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Volgograd, Russia

HABITAT REGENERATION STRATEGIES USING OIKONET
Interaction of OIKONet partners

Viera Jeklová, Elena Krašňáková, Larisa Kuzina
viera.jeklova@stuba.sk, elena.krasnyakova@gmail.com, larisa_kuzina@yandex.ru

Matrix of Interaction of OIKONet Partners

	Faculty of Architecture STU	Faculty of Architecture VSUACE
STAGE 1 The concept of urban planning regeneration	OIKONET WORKSPACE Habitat Regeneration Strategies	
	Preparation of a task on Petržalka Exploring the examples on regeneration strategies worldwide Analysis of the area, strategy development	Comparative analysis and discussion Exploring the examples on regeneration strategies worldwide Concept of urban planning regeneration
STAGE 2 The project of regeneration	Collaboration in the network Workspace Habitat Regeneration Strategies	
	Conceptual model design Consultations and commenting the regeneration strategies	Choice of a block in the territory of Petržalka for implementing the project of regeneration on the basis of methods of flexibility and sustainability of residential structures

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FASTU - Faculty of Architecture Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, 24 - 25 September 2015

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Architecture, "Gabriele d'Annunzio" University, Chieti-Pescara, Italy

PEOPLE MEET IN PETRŽALKA
The requalification of a post-socialist neighbourhood

Nicola Potocci
nicola.potocci@unich.it, nicolapotocci@strala.com

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Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology Bratislava

GLOBAL DWELLING: HOUSING REGENERATION STRATEGIES
CASE STUDY - Bratislava Devínska nová Ves - Volkswagen Slovakia
Regeneration of the problematic site between Volkswagen Slovakia factory and existing housing in Devínska nová Ves in purpose of creating a polyfunctional zone with accommodation for Volkswagen employees

Jural Furek, Tibor Volcsek
jural.furek@stuba.sk, tibor.volcsek@stuba.sk

VISUALIZATION (1) OF THE PROJECT SCHEME AND DESIGN

INSPIRATIONS (1) FROM EXISTING PROJECTS LISTED BELOW

CONCEPT (1) URBANISM AND PROBLEM ANALYSIS

ANALYSIS (1) URBANISM AND PROBLEM (2)

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Bialystok University of Technology, Poland

NEW HOUSING IN POLAND - URBAN AND ARCHITECTURAL IDEAS
Large Estates - Gated Communities

Andrzej Tobojak
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FASTU - Faculty of Architecture Slovak University of Technology Bratislava, 24 - 25 September 2015

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Bialystok University of Technology, Poland

NEW HOUSING IN POLAND - URBAN AND ARCHITECTURAL IDEAS
Large Estates - Traditional City Structures

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SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: GLOBAL DWELLING
 (ACTS) - Faculty of Architecture, Bialystok University of Technology, Białystok, 28 - 31 September 2015

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Bialystok University of Technology, Poland

NEW HOUSING IN POLAND - URBAN AND ARCHITECTURAL IDEAS
Urban Implants / City Villas / Postindustrial Revitalization

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 (ACTS) - Faculty of Architecture, Bialystok University of Technology, Białystok, 28 - 31 September 2015

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Bialystok University of Technology, Poland

NEW HOUSING IN POLAND - URBAN AND ARCHITECTURAL IDEAS
Uniques

Andrzej Tekajuk
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 (ACTS) - Faculty of Architecture, Bialystok University of Technology, Białystok, 28 - 31 September 2015

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Bialystok University of Technology, Poland

NEW HOUSING IN POLAND - URBAN AND ARCHITECTURAL IDEAS
High-rise buildings

Andrzej Tekajuk
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Rehabitar el cerro: Registro de memoria del cerro
Merced Valparaiso

CURSO URBANISMO AVANZADO 2
A course for urbanists in a multidisciplinary format, for 10 days

Saludo Noviembre 15

FERIA DEL RECUERDO

Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, Riga Technical University, Latvia

CASE STUDY OF CPTED WORKSHOP IN RIGA
Creating links between learning practice and stakeholders in the process of urban refurbishment

Edgars Bondars, Sandra Treņa, Uģis Strašūns
edgars.bondars@rtu.lv, sandra.trenja@rtu.lv, ugis.straus@rtu.lv

Objective demonstrated:
- in practice
- Riga Technical University
- State Police of Latvia
- Riga Municipality
- Riga City Council
- Riga City Police
- Riga City Planning and Construction Department
- Riga City Environmental Design Experts

The aim of the workshop:
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga

The main objectives of the project:
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga

The benefits of involving the actors:
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga
- to create an environment solution design proposal for the area of Nīča Street in Riga

Eötvös Loránd University and Hungarian Academy of Sciences, TK Budapest

THE ROLE OF GLOBALIZATION IN THE GENTRIFICATION PROCESSES OF THE INNER CITIES
Example of Budapest

Adrienne Csizmady, Gergely Olt
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Main findings:

- The postmodern consumer can be characterized by active consumer behaviors. Patterns of consumption are more and more globalized.
- The change in consumption habits affect the spatial patterns of consumption as well.
- The use of cities is changing. The inner cities of European capitals are typically becoming places of consumption and entertainment.
- Global effects shape the landscapes of inner cities: similar neighborhoods emerge in different parts of the world.
- City development efforts turned in the direction of cultural and consumption oriented developments.
- Cultural initiatives are often the catalysts and legitimating factors of the developments.
- Gentrification and stigmatization processes in the inner city became more pronounced in Central-Eastern Europe – they are often fueled by the culture oriented developments
- We see similar processes in Budapest and in bigger rural towns.
- These changes often generate social conflicts.

IN THE LIFE OF THE CITIES, IN THEIR GLOBAL REPRESENTATIONS AND EVEN IN THEIR ECONOMIC SUCCESS, LOCAL MEANS AND THE INSPIRING ENVIRONMENT CAN BE AN IMPORTANT FACTOR.

The evolution of the ruin pub scene

1988-2004
The first privately owned official cultural entertainment venues opened. After the abolition and relocation of the tenants the first ruin pubs opened in the deteriorating council owned buildings

2005-2009
The local authority turned against the ruin pubs, the demolition of the buildings started and the rent contracts were not renewed. Some venues with pronounced cultural missions could find new home in the area – as the second generation of ruin pub.

2010-2014
The only way to use any empty retail space or building became opening a pub. The cultural mission was overshadowed by commercial functions mostly for tourists.

Observations of sustainability

- The artistic and creative milieu is displaced by the commercial gentrification
- Tourism and entertainment consumption is growing
- Tension between residents and day-time users and the night-time economy is increasing
- The milieu of the neighborhood is changing

Budapest – Main features of the changes in Inner-Esztebékterv

- The demolition of the housing stock – often in cultural heritage status – built at the late 19th early 20th century
- Acceleration of the demolition process between 2004-2006. Occurrence of new building – often not fitting in the environment
- The 2008 crisis stopped the process and in its empty buildings (legal and illegal forms) of intermediate use appeared – often in the forms of ruin bars.
- New places of consumption emerged at the expense of the market functions
- The change caused serious conflicts.

Széchenyi István University, Győr and Hungarian Academy of Sciences, TK Budapest

RECONSTRUCTION, SPATIAL TRAUMAS, DISPLACEMENT
Research proposal (example of Budapest)

Dezso Eklér, Adrienne Csizmady
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Theoretical background

One can only reside locally but not globally, living one's personal life at a certain place where life narratives intertwine with experienced space narratives. The spatial stories of the city get written in the architectural language and are layered as spatial texts.

Cities as spatial texts compose a palimpsest structure: the spatial narratives of the centuries get written on top of one another: stories of houses in the streets and squares can be read like letters on the pages of a codex. The original spatial texts are preserved at some places, and new spatial stories are built at other places, concealing the old ones.

Demolitions and reconstructions are traumatic events, since the new spatial narratives cannot be interpreted by the language of previous spatial texts.

These traumas of space cause mass traumas of life, and are usually lived with being displaced or excluded (e.g. gentrification). Everyone is torn into a given spatial story, familiar with its language, and identifies oneself with it (neighborhood paradise). The rebuilding and/or leaving behind the living area are a traumatic experience also because the new spatial texts cannot be interpreted by the notions through the language of the old spatial stories. (The personal life traumas force their victims to speaklessness as the tragic event cannot be told in the language of their lives or that time).

The globalizing world today can rebuild our environment in a generation's lifetime. The loss of the familiar living spaces (trauma of space) has become an everyday phenomenon and the cause of mass life traumas. Losing our local ties and, through this, our personal space stories, has become a mass experience. We must accept that we can only "dwell globally", and not place-identically anymore. This in itself is absurd, just like faithlessness.

Budapest – three centuries of the old Jewish district

1730 – The building of houses starts in the gardens outside the medieval wall. The citizens tried to hinder such constructions of the sectors.

1730 – The spatial structure of today was formed by the parcelling out the gardens, and opening roads. On the city plots a rural suburb is born of poor private houses, the majority of whose residents are manual workers.

1800 – Following Joseph II's edict of religious tolerance the Jewish moved to this area. The hundred years long royal housing canon order began. Huge blocks of flats were built on the city plots. By the end of the 19th century the baroque-classicist town was transformed into a metropolis of multi-story houses with closed courtyards.

1944 – The district inhabited by high proportion of Jewish people became the ghetto of Budapest, as the fascist authorities surrounded it by walls and fences. The area became the space of an extreme deprivation of familiarity.

1950 – Private blocks of flats are taken into public ownership. Flats get divided into money, decreasing. Some owners are forced to share their flats with others.

1950 – During the collectivization of the communist era under the pressure of collective loss of remembrance Jewish identity carried by the subject of social discourse. However, being tied to the location remains part of the residents' identity up to now, even if repressed.

1980 – The change of the political regime is connected to the revival of the Jewish identity, urban planning serves as a tool of strengthening cultural traditions. Property privatization has a counter-effect: it results in mass moving out. The construction of sleeping quarters have a counter-orientation effect: small shops and workshops went bankrupt. Families with children moved to the agglomeration areas.

2008 – With the boom of real estate market foreign investors arrived and the relocation of the tenants began. Large number of houses left vacant due to speculative purposes and profit oriented developments. During the vacant houses gave opportunity for intermediary usage: cultural entertainment venues moved in.

2008 – The demolition of historic housing stock and partial the light to new Jewish architectural language initiatives. At the same time new areas of consumption are created ("ruin pubs").

2010 – Birth of the entertainment quarter generated by low cost airlines, and international branch industry. Although becoming an "entertainment quarter" meant the revival of local traditions, it could not slow down the process of mobility out.

Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden

COMPACT CITIES?

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Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden

HOUSING REGENERATION

Research on involvement of residents in management and refurbishment
Jenny Stenberg@chalmers.se | Lasse Frykholm@work.gu.se

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Faculty of Architecture, campus Sint-Lucas Gent, KU Leuven, Belgium

A multi-criteria approach to compare urban regeneration scenarios of former industrial areas. The case of Tirana North Boulevard extension.
Arch. Julian Veleštnja | Researcher in Public Urbanism, Urban and Regional Planning at Department of Urbanism, Faculty of Architecture, University of Tirana, Albania
Arch. Dorina Papa | Researcher and PhD candidate in the joint program Public Urbanism, Faculty of Architecture, University of Tirana, Albania

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Faculty of architecture, campus Sint-Lucas Gent, KU Leuven, Belgium

Threshold Matters Workshop is a learning space with an OIKONET research project. Students are encouraged to explore how the workshop influence the processes of learning and the process of the public.
prof. dr. Jozsef Veleštnja, dr. architect Tomaz Gama
prof. dr. Jozsef Veleštnja, dr. architect Tomaz Gama

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A.5 Posters for the Belgrade workshop

Posters of the preparatory activities done for the third international workshop in Belgrade.

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PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

WORKSHOP: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA, SLOVENIA, JUNE 9-11 2016

Living Learning Programme

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PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
SAINTS CYRIL AND METHODIUS UNIVERSITY, SKOPJE, REPUBLIC OF MACEDONIA

WORKSHOP: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF SKOPJE, REPUBLIC OF MACEDONIA, JUNE 9-11 2016

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PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
GEBZE TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY, TURKEY

WORKSHOP: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE, SERBIA, JUNE 9-11 2016

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ISCTE IUL
University Institute of Lisbon

PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
ISCTE - INSTITUTO UNIVERSITARIO DE LISBOA, LISBON, PORTUGAL

LOCALIZATION

CHRONOLOGY

ANALYSIS OF INFRASTRUCTURES
Collect infrastructure in relevant areas

SECTIONS

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KU LEUVEN

PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
SINT LUCAS FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE, KU LEUVEN, BRUSSELS / GHENT, BELGIUM

A MICRO SCALE OBSERVATION ON THE INFORMALITY OF KOSANCIJEV VENAC.
Tinka Šušter, Ivana Križanović, Anđelka Bekić, Nata Pačić

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VUKOBROD STATE UNIVERSITY OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION VISALJE

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THE NAME OF YOUR UNIVERSITY GOES HERE, CITY, COUNTRY.

TASK 5
Prof. Eliza Križanović, Doc. Vladimir Ruzanov, Asst. Larisa Popovic, Danil Šaranac, Vlast Štapićević, Marina Strelak
Proposing Strategies created

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b-tu
Brandenburgische Technische Universität Cottbus

PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
BRANDENBURGISCHE TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT COTTBUS, BTU, COTTBUS, GERMANY

BELGRADE WATERFRONT

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PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
IUC, Institut d'Urbanisme de Grenoble, Grenoble, France

Localization of Belgrade

Belgrade is the capital of Serbia. The country is part of the Balkans in South East of Europe.

The development of Belgrade from 19th century into 21 century

The urban morphology of Kosancicev Venac

It shows the main elements in the architecture and functions in Kosancicev Venac.

Our reference: Euromediterranean project
Euromediterranean project located in Marseille South of France. It's a big project who started in 1995. His goal was to regenerate the harbour and the old town (19th and 20th industrial sites). They develop a new kind of economy, a big improvement of culture and a revitalization of districts.

A district integrate in the city of Belgrade

With the mobility (tram, roads, bike...) we observe Kosancicev Venac is an area with easily access, close to the old city. The district has a big potential in the regeneration.

The development of Kosancicev Venac in Belgrade from XVII century until 1941

Diagnostic conclusions

- An architectural district of Belgrade
- A great potential in housing: Venac for tourism and of revitalizing
- Area's strong identity and landscape

Our approach of revitalization: urban renewal

- The intervention must be phased in the periods
- The architectural character
- Strongly preserve public utility and landscape
- The other several urban renewal urban renewal states
- Urban renewal architectural development
- Urban renewal architectural design
- Urban renewal architectural development

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PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: RENEWING / REVITALIZING: CREATING LIVABLE CITIES
DUBLIN SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE, DIT, IRELAND.

O'DEWANEY GARDENS, DUBLIN CITY COUNCIL HOUSING REGENERATION
Comparing proposed housing regeneration proposals
Andrew Mc Alister & Sean Barrett

INTRODUCTION
The O'Dewaneey Garden Local Authority, the garden was constructed in the 1930s consisting of 24 blocks and 1500 housing units. There is a local secondary school, St. Paul's, and an industrial site, the O'Dewaneey Park, in the area by St. Paul's Primary School and to the west of O'Dewaneey Gardens.
There are three principal objectives with the site, one of which is to regenerate the area of O'Dewaneey Gardens. The regeneration of the area will be for the benefit of the city's original society. The O'Dewaneey Gardens is a 'strongly identified' area, with a high level of social cohesion and a strong sense of community. The regeneration of the area will be for the benefit of the city's original society. The O'Dewaneey Gardens is a 'strongly identified' area, with a high level of social cohesion and a strong sense of community.

EXISTING HOUSING SCHEME **DEVELOPER PROPOSAL** **CITY COUNCIL PROPOSAL** **DSA DIT STUDENT PROPOSAL**

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PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES: Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Livable Cities
BIALYSTOK UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, POLAND

ANALYSIS AND INSPIRATIONS
Analysis of communications and composition. Comparison of architectural and urban contrast. Inspirations for further project.

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Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava

KOSANČIČEV VENAC, BELGRADE

EUROVEA, BRATISLAVA

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